

EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF SURGICAL INTERVENTION IN INTRAOCULAR LENS SUBLUXATION IN THE PEDIATRIC POPULATION

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Abstract. *This article presents an analysis of two clinical cases of late postoperative complications following congenital cataract extraction in children, accompanied by intraocular lens (IOL) subluxation and iris capture. It is shown that displacement of the IOL leads to pupil deformation and a decrease in visual functions. Based on clinical observations, the effectiveness of a combined surgical approach involving iridoplasty is demonstrated. The study concludes that preventive iridoplasty is advisable when iris capture is detected in order to form a functional pupil and prevent recurrence of complications. The aim of the study was to analyze clinical cases of IOL subluxation after cataract extraction with intraocular lens implantation and to identify the features of the applied surgical treatment strategy.*

Keywords: *congenital cataract, intraocular lens subluxation, iridoplasty, postoperative complications.*

Introduction

Surgical treatment of congenital cataract in children remains one of the major complex problems in ophthalmic practice. Despite advances in minimally invasive technologies, a high incidence of late complications after cataract extraction persists in pediatric patients, among which intraocular lens (IOL) subluxation occupies a leading position. According to the literature, the incidence of IOL displacement in childhood ranges from 5% to 20%, which is significantly higher than in adult patients [1,2,3,9]. The increased risk is associated with anatomical and physiological features of the pediatric eye, including a prolonged period of eyeball growth, increased elasticity of the capsular–zonular apparatus, pronounced postoperative inflammatory response, as well as a tendency toward synechiae formation and capsular contraction [4,5,14,15].

Decentration or subluxation of the IOL leads to reduced visual quality, abnormal pupil shape, higher-order aberrations, and an increased risk of amblyopia. In the absence of timely correction, this complication may result in persistent visual impairment or childhood disability [6,7,8,12]. The choice of optimal surgical tactics for late IOL displacement in children remains debatable. Repositioning, stabilization, IOL exchange, or combined surgical interventions should be selected individually, taking into account the anatomical and functional condition of the eye and the severity of the complication [8,10,11,13]. The presented clinical cases demonstrate an approach to selecting surgical treatment tactics for late IOL subluxation in a child after congenital cataract removal.

The aim of the study was to analyze clinical cases of IOL subluxation after cataract extraction and implantation of an intraocular lens, and to identify the characteristics of the applied surgical treatment strategy.

Materials and Methods. We analyzed clinical observation cases of patients N.M. and Kh.A. treated at the ophthalmology department of the clinic of Tashkent State Medical University. Patient N.M., born on May 27, 2014 (10 years old), from Namangan region, Namangan city.

Complaints: according to the mother, a change in pupil shape and decreased visual acuity of the left eye.

Patient Kh.A., born on September 20, 2013 (9 years old), from Andijan region.

Complaints: according to the mother, change in pupil shape of the right eye, decreased visual acuity, and discomfort in bright light.

The patients underwent comprehensive ophthalmological examinations, clinical and laboratory investigations, as well as consultations with related specialists (otolaryngologist, pediatrician, neurosurgeon, neurologist).

Results. Patient Kh.A. Anamnesis morbi: According to the mother, the disease was first noticed at the age of three years, when the parents observed a change in the color of the pupil of the right eye. The patient consulted an ophthalmologist at the local place of residence and was diagnosed with congenital cataract of the right eye (OD) and referred to the clinic of TashPMI, where planned surgical treatment was recommended. On 07.10.2022, the patient underwent surgery: OD – total cataract extraction with intraocular lens implantation (+19.0 D). The early postoperative period was uneventful. One year after surgery, the parents noticed a change in the shape of the pupil of the right eye and sought medical care at the TashPMI clinic. Examination revealed IOL subluxation with partial iris capture. The diagnosis of OD – IOL subluxation was established, and surgical treatment was recommended. On 19.10.2023, the patient underwent OD – IOL reposition and synechiotomy. The postoperative course was stable, with improvement in visual acuity. However, at a follow-up examination six months later, the parents again reported decreased visual acuity and pupil deformation. Status oculorum: OD – Calm, no pathological discharge. The cornea is transparent. The anterior chamber is of moderate depth, aqueous humor is clear. The pupil is black, oval, deformed, and displaced upward. The optical part of the IOL is displaced upward by 1 mm. Iris capture of the IOL haptic element is noted from 11 to 1 o'clock. Fundus reflex is uneven pink. Extraocular movements are full. OS – Calm, no pathological discharge. The cornea is transparent, the anterior chamber is of moderate depth, aqueous humor is clear. Iris structure and relief are preserved. The pupil is round, black, with preserved reaction. The lens is transparent. Fundus reflex is pink. Extraocular movements are full.

Fundus examination: OU – The optic disc is round with clear margins, pale pink in color, vascular caliber preserved. Visual acuity: Visus OD/OS = 0.2 (uncorrected) / 1.0. B-scan ultrasonography: Retina attached, vitreous body without echopathology. A-scan: 22.85 mm / 22.90 mm. Laboratory findings: Complete blood count, urinalysis, stool analysis, and blood biochemistry were within normal limits. ECG showed sinus rhythm. Blood tests for HIV, hepatitis B and C were negative.

Specialist consultations:

Pediatrician – no acute somatic pathology.

Otolaryngologist – ENT organs without pathology.

Neurologist – no abnormalities detected.

Based on the clinical findings, the diagnosis of OD – IOL subluxation was confirmed. Repeat surgical treatment was performed: OD – synechiotomy, IOL reposition, partial anterior vitrectomy, and iridoplasty.

Surgical procedure:

The operative field was treated with betadine. A blepharostat was applied. Paracentesis was performed at the 8 o'clock position. Viscoelastic was injected into the anterior chamber. Iris revision revealed flat synechiae from 11 to 1 o'clock with IOL capture, which were dissected using a microspatula and Vannas scissors. The IOL was repositioned into the posterior chamber. Partial anterior vitrectomy was performed. A 3.0 mm central opening was created in the posterior capsule. Iridoplasty was carried out using a modified McCannel technique with 10-0 suture material, achieving restoration of a central, round pupil. The anterior chamber was irrigated with saline solution followed by 0.1% dexamethasone solution. Paracentesis hydration was performed, sterile air was injected, and subconjunctival injections of dexamethasone and ceftriaxone (0.3 ml each) were administered. An aseptic monocular dressing was applied.

Postoperative treatment included topical dexamethasone 0.1% eye drops administered hourly and moxifloxacin 0.5% eye drops six times daily. On the first postoperative day, the surgical wound was clean, sutures were intact, the cornea was transparent, the anterior chamber was of moderate depth, and the aqueous humor was clear. The pupil was round and centrally located. The IOL position was central, and intraocular pressure was within normal limits. At discharge, the patient's general condition was satisfactory. Ophthalmological examination revealed a clear cornea, central and round pupil with coloboma at 12 o'clock, central IOL position, pink fundus reflex, and normal intraocular pressure. Visual acuity was OD – 0.5 and OS – 1.0.

During a 1.5-year follow-up period, the operated eye remained stable with no signs of recurrent iris capture or IOL dislocation. Visual acuity was preserved, indicating a positive outcome of the surgical intervention. Patient N.M. Anamnesis morbi: According to the mother, the disease was noticed at the age of two years when a gray coloration of the pupils of both eyes was observed. The patient was referred to the clinic of Tashkent State Medical University, where the diagnosis of OU – congenital cataract was established. On 05.04.2022, OD – total cataract extraction with IOL implantation (+20.0 D) under capsular tension ring support was performed. On 08.06.2022, OS – total cataract extraction with IOL implantation (+19.0 D) and basal iridectomy was carried out. The patient was discharged in satisfactory condition.

At a six-month follow-up examination, both eyes were calm with transparent corneas and clear aqueous humor. In the right eye, the pupil was oval, the IOL was centrally positioned, and uneven posterior capsule opacification was noted. In the left eye, superior IOL displacement from 10 to 12 o'clock with iris capture was detected. The optical part of the IOL remained central, while the haptics were not visualized. The pupil was deformed due to traction of the iris margin. Extraocular movements were full in both eyes.

Figure 1. Patient: iris capture of the pupil by the haptic element of the intraocular lens in the left eye before surgery.

Visual acuity: Visus OD/OS = 0.6 (uncorrected) / 0.1 (eccentric fixation).
B-scan ultrasonography: OU – vitreous body without echopathology, retina attached.

A-scan: 23.10 mm / 22.72 mm.

Laboratory findings: Complete blood count, urinalysis, stool analysis, and blood biochemistry were within normal limits. ECG revealed sinus rhythm. Blood tests for HIV, hepatitis B and C were negative.

Specialist consultations: Pediatric examination – no acute somatic pathology detected.

Otolaryngological examination – ENT organs without pathology.

Neurological examination – asthenoneurotic syndrome.

Based on the above findings, the clinical diagnosis of OS – intraocular lens subluxation was established. Therefore, surgical treatment was performed: OS – synechiotomy, IOL reposition, partial anterior vitrectomy, and iridoplasty. Surgical procedure: The operative field was treated with betadine. A blepharostat was applied to the left eye. Paracentesis was performed at the 8 o'clock position. Viscoelastic was injected into the anterior chamber. Iris revision using a spatula revealed flat synechiae from 11 to 2 o'clock with IOL capture. The synechiae were dissected using a microspatula and Vannas scissors. The IOL was repositioned into the posterior chamber. Partial anterior vitrectomy was performed. Fibrosis of the posterior capsule was noted, with a central opening measuring 3.0 mm.

Iridoplasty was performed using a modified McCannel technique with 10-0 suture material. Approximation of the iris edges was achieved, restoring a central and round pupil. A full-thickness corneal entry into the anterior chamber was made. Under visual control, the peripheral iris edge in the defect area was sequentially grasped and sutured. A second pass was performed to fix the opposite iris segment, after which the suture was externalized through the cornea. Knot formation was performed using a Zinsky instrument, resulting in a single secure suture and adequate approximation of the iris edges with restoration of the central pupil position. The pupil became round.

The anterior chamber was irrigated with saline solution followed by 0.1% dexamethasone solution. Hydration of the paracentesis site was performed, and sterile air was injected into the anterior chamber. Subconjunctival injections of dexamethasone and ceftriaxone (0.3 ml each) were administered. Antiseptic eye drops were instilled, and an aseptic monocular dressing was applied. Postoperative topical treatment included dexamethasone 0.1% eye drops (2 drops hourly), moxifloxacin 0.5% eye drops (2 drops six times daily), and Kufen Forte 0.5% eye drops (2 drops three times daily).

First postoperative day:

OS – surgical wound clean, sutures intact, cornea transparent, anterior chamber of moderate depth, aqueous humor clear. The pupil was centrally located and round. An air bubble was present in the pupillary area. The IOL position was central. Intraocular pressure was within normal limits.

At discharge: The patient's general condition was satisfactory. Body temperature was 36.6°C. Vesicular breathing was noted in the lungs. Heart sounds were rhythmic. The abdomen was soft and painless, with regular bowel movements and diuresis.

OS – calm, no pathological discharge. The surgical wound was clean, sutures intact. The cornea was transparent, the anterior chamber was of moderate depth, and the aqueous humor was clear. The pupil was centrally located and round (Figure 2), with coloboma at the 12 o'clock

position. The IOL position was central. Fundus reflex was pink. Intraocular pressure was within normal limits. Visual acuity at discharge: Visus OD – 0.6; OS – 0.8.

Figure 2. Patient: centrally located, round pupil after surgical treatment.

The combined surgical intervention made it possible to eliminate the mechanical iris capture and restore the anatomy of the anterior segment. In the postoperative period, the patient was followed up dynamically by an ophthalmologist with regular examinations. During the two-year follow-up after surgery, a stable ophthalmological condition was observed, with no signs of recurrent iris capture or dislocation of the optical elements of the intraocular lens. Functional outcomes, including visual acuity, remained at high levels, indicating a sustained positive anatomical and functional result of the performed intervention.

Conclusion. Clinical observation demonstrated the characteristic manifestations of a mechanical IOL-related complication, namely iris capture of the lens and pupil deformation. Analysis of the therapeutic measures showed that the combination of synechiotomy, IOL reposition, vitrectomy, and iridoplasty is an effective method for eliminating this complication. The obtained data indicate that iridolenticular capture of the intraocular lens in pediatric patients leads to persistent dysfunction of the iris sphincter, accompanied by pupil deformation and insufficiency. Under conditions of ongoing traction, there is a high risk of recurrent pupil capture and secondary subluxation of the optical part of the IOL. Therefore, when iris capture is detected, performing iridoplasty using a modified McCannel technique with 10-0 suture material is advisable. This approach allows restoration of the central position and round shape of the pupil, enabling the formation of a functional pupil with a diameter of approximately 3 mm and preventing recurrent involvement of the iris in the IOL area.

REFERENCES

1. Egorov E.A., Katargina L.A. Pediatric Ophthalmology. Moscow: GEOTAR-Media; 2019.
2. Katargina L.A., Sidorenko E.I. Congenital Cataract in Children. Moscow: Meditsina; 2018.
3. Katargina L.A. Late complications of congenital cataract surgery in children. Bulletin of Ophthalmology. 2020;3:45–52.
4. Nazirova Z.R., Turakulova D.M., Buzrukov S.B. Surgical treatment of congenital glaucoma in children using the GlauTex drainage device. Bulletin of Ophthalmology. 2020;136(6-2):202–206.

5. Nazirova Z.R. The role of local inflammation and immune response in allergic eye diseases in children. *Medical News*. 2017;2:82–84.
6. Nazirova Z.R., Turakulova D.M., Buzrukov B.T. Analysis of examination and treatment outcomes in children with congenital glaucoma. *Modern Technologies in Ophthalmology*. 2020;3:124–125.
7. Malyugin B.E., Pashtaev N.P. *Intraocular Correction of Aphakia*. Moscow: Oftalmologiya; 2016.
8. Fedorov S.N., Zakharov V.D. *Cataract Surgery in Children*. Moscow: Eye Microsurgery; 2017.
9. Apple D.J., Mamalis N. *Complications of Intraocular Lenses*. Baltimore: Williams & Wilkins; 2000.
10. Vasavada A.R., Nihalani B.R. Pediatric cataract surgery. *Current Opinion in Ophthalmology*. 2006;17:54–61.
11. Koch C.R., Kohnen T. Decentration and dislocation of intraocular lenses. *Journal of Cataract & Refractive Surgery*. 1997.
12. Plager D.A., Yang S. Complications in pediatric cataract surgery. *Current Opinion in Ophthalmology*. 2012.
13. Wilson M.E., Trivedi R.H. *Pediatric Cataract Surgery: Techniques, Complications, and Management*. Springer; 2014.
14. Zetterström C., Kugelberg U. Posterior capsule opacification and intraocular lens complications in children. *British Journal of Ophthalmology*. 2005.
15. Lambert S.R. Long-term outcomes after pediatric cataract surgery. *Transactions of the American Ophthalmological Society*. 2010.